

INITIAL POST-BUCKLING BEHAVIOURS OF COMPOSITE SHALLOW SHELLS AND PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Koiter's initial post-buckling theory has been successfully implemented into finite element context. This theory is capable of qualitatively estimating structural stability at the neighbourhood of bifurcation point and predicting the structural sensitivity to initial imperfection. However, Koiter's theory has never been adopted by any mainstream finite element codes although a large number of papers were published during last decades to attempt to contribute. The long-existing problem is that numerical results encountered the computational convergence problem when adopting B-notation for finite element formulations. In this paper, the newly-established N-notation formulations with characteristics of commutativity of displacements have been applied so that the initial post-buckling theory can be derived directly through the energy's point of view. Most importantly, the convergence problem or mesh sensitivity is no more the hurdle of implementation of Koiter's theory into finite element. To validate the approach proposed here, two kinds of structural configurations, shallow shells and plates, have been simulated and the numerical results have been compared with analytical ones. Satisfactory agreements have been achieved in the terms of buckling loads and two initial post-buckling coefficients.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite shell structure is of a profound interest in the aerospace application. While the buckling problem, pertaining to the structural stability near the bifurcation point, is always a concern to the engineers. Ever since the beginning of last century, many researchers had been engaged with buckling problems of cylindrical shells under compression [1-3]. The disagreement between analytical results and experimental data was the nightmare and lasted for decades. From the potential energy's point of view, Koiter applied perturbation method at the neighbourhood of bifurcation point to discover the intrinsic nature of structural stability [4]. The finding was that the stability is determined by the signs of cubic and quartic energy terms of displacement. Meanwhile, structural sensitivity to imperfection can be estimated through these values as well. A revisiting research to this theory was conducted by Budiansky [5] where the asymptotic expression of loading-carrying capacity was proposed with introduction of two initial post-buckling coefficients. Initial post-buckling behaviours of structure have been encapsulated by these two coefficients.

Although Koiter's theory is of great prominence for the study of structural stability, the implementation of this theory has never been successfully implemented into finite element environment due to the mesh sensitivity or computational problem. The reason is that when adopting the principle of virtual work, i.e. B-notation for finite element formulations, the initial post-buckling stresses would get involved into the calculation of initial post-buckling curvature. As well known in finite element framework, accuracy of stresses would be compromised to some extent when they are estimated through the interpolation of displacements [6-8]. However, the second initial post-buckling

curvature is determined by difference of two close terms and hence any loss of accuracy would lead to a catastrophic distortion of results, i.e. locking problem [9-12].

The achievement from authors' previous paper is that a finite element formulation with commutativity in terms of displacements have been explicitly constructed [13]. With aid of this significant feature of finite element formulation, the initial post-buckling theory could be derived in the context of finite element with the principle of stationary potential energy at the first time. The most important contribution is that without dealing with initial post-buckling stresses, the locking problem could be elegantly resolved. In this paper, two kinds of structural configurations, shells and plates, have been employed for the numerical validations.

2 ANALYTICAL DERIVATIONS OF INITIAL POST-BUCKLING BEHAVIOURS OF SIMPLY SUPPORTED SHALLOW SHELLS AND PLATES UNDER COMPRESSION

To derive the analytical formulations, the same method as employed in Koiter's thesis, i.e. perturbation method, should be used as well as follows.

$$w = w^0 + \xi w^1 + \xi^2 w^2 + \dots \quad (1.a)$$

$$\phi = \phi^0 + \xi \phi^1 + \xi^2 \phi^2 + \dots \quad (1.b)$$

$$\lambda = \lambda^c (1 + a\xi + b\xi^2 + \dots) \quad (1.c)$$

where w is the deflection and ϕ the Airy stress function. The superscripts of these two notations indicate the levels of perturbation, *viz.* 0 for pre-buckling, 1 for buckling or first perturbation and 2 for secondary perturbation. ξ is a scalar, the perturbation parameter and can be considered as the amplitude of buckling mode. λ is the loading parameter and λ^c signifies the buckling load. a and b are the initial post-buckling parameters.

Based on Donnell's formulation for cylindrical shells and Kirchhoff plate theory, Dong introduced the governing differential equation of laminated cylindrical shells [14].

Figure 1: curved shell under axial compression

Through the substitutions of equation (1) into Dong's formulation, governing equations of cross-ply cylindrical shells subject to compression along the longitudinal direction as shown in Fig.1 for the buckling and secondary perturbation can be written as

$$\begin{cases} a_{22}\phi_{,xxxx}^1 + (2a_{12} + a_{66})\phi_{,xxyy}^1 + a_{11}\phi_{,yyyy}^1 - \frac{1}{R}w_{,xx}^1 = 0 \\ d_{11}w_{,xxxx}^1 + 2(d_{12} + 2d_{66})w_{,xxyy}^1 + d_{22}w_{,yyyy}^1 + \lambda^c w_{,xx}^1 + \frac{1}{R}\phi_{,xx}^1 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.a)$$

$$\begin{cases} a_{22}\phi_{,xxxx}^2 + (2a_{12} + a_{66})\phi_{,xxyy}^2 + a_{11}\phi_{,yyyy}^2 - \frac{1}{R}w_{,xx}^2 = -w_{,xx}^1 w_{,yy}^1 + w_{,xy}^1 w_{,xy}^1 \\ d_{11}w_{,xxxx}^2 + 2(d_{12} + 2d_{66})w_{,xxyy}^2 + d_{22}w_{,yyyy}^2 + \frac{1}{R}\phi_{,xx}^2 = w_{,xx}^1 \phi_{,yy}^1 - 2w_{,xy}^1 \phi_{,xy}^1 + w_{,yy}^1 \phi_{,xx}^1 - a\lambda^c w_{,xx}^1 \end{cases} \quad (2.b)$$

where a_{ij} are the constants of inverse matrix of extensional stiffness of the classic laminate theory and d_{ij} the constants of bending stiffness matrix. The buckling mode and secondary perturbation mode can be written respectively as

$$w^1 = t \sin k \beta x \sin \beta y \quad (3.b)$$

$$w^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} t \varpi_{ij} \sin i k_0 \beta x \sin \beta y \quad (3.c)$$

where t is assigned to be the thickness of shell. $\beta = \pi/B$ and $k = mB/L$ with m being the number of half waves along the axial direction. There is only one half-wave in the circumferential direction as dictated by the nature of uniaxial compression. According to the expressions of a and b in Budiansky's work [15], buckling loads and these two initial post-buckling coefficients can be finally determined as

$$\lambda^c = \frac{\beta^2 (d_{11} k^4 + 2(d_{12} + 2d_{66}) k^2 + d_{22})}{k^2} + \frac{k^2}{R^2 \beta^2 (a_{22} k^4 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) k^2 + a_{11})} \quad (4.a)$$

$$a = \frac{8}{\lambda^c} \frac{1 - (-1)^m}{m \pi^2} \frac{k^2 t}{R (a_{22} k^4 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) k^2 + a_{11})} \quad (4.b)$$

$$b = \frac{1}{\lambda^c} \left[\frac{t^2 k^2 \beta^2}{16 a_{11}} + \frac{t^2 \beta^2}{16 k^2 a_{22}} + \frac{64t}{R \pi^2} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{k^2 \varpi_{ij}}{(a_{22} k^4 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) k^2 + a_{11})} + \frac{\varpi_{ij}}{2 \left[a_{22} \left(\frac{i k_0}{j} \right)^2 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) + a_{11} \left(\frac{j}{i k_0} \right)^2 \right] j^2} \right\} \times \left(\frac{2i^2 - i^2 j^2 + 2m^2 j^2}{i(i^2 - 4m^2)} \frac{1}{j(j^2 - 4)} \right) \right] \quad (4.c)$$

When it comes to the plate, these values can be simplified as

$$\lambda^c = \frac{\beta^2 (d_{11} k^4 + 2(d_{12} + 2d_{66}) k^2 + d_{22})}{k^2} \quad (5.a)$$

$$a = 0 \quad (5.b)$$

$$b = \frac{1}{\lambda^c} \left(\frac{t^2 k^2 \beta^2}{16 a_{11}} + \frac{t^2 \beta^2}{16 k^2 a_{22}} \right) \quad (5.c)$$

It can be found that the first initial post-buckling coefficient a can either be zero or nonzero which counts on the value of m . The even values of m can produce a vanishing value of a hence a symmetric initial post-buckling behaviour emerges. To plate, a remains zero and b positive which implies that the initial post-buckling behaviour is stable and structure is not sensitive to imperfection. But to shell, the sign of b is not predictable.

3 REPRODUCTIONS OF SIMPLY-SUPPORTED SHELLS UNDER COMPRESION

In the previous section, the analytical derivations for the initial post-buckling of simply supported shell and plate have been delivered. To validate the formulations of commutative N-notation used for

the finite element analysis, especially for the initial post-buckling analysis, the reproductions of these two scenarios have been carried out herein. This section is focused on shells.

3.1 Numerical models

Simply supported shells subject to axial compression have been numerically simulated. Laminate with cross-ply layups has been considered. Thickness of each layer is 0.125mm. The material properties have been listed in Table 1. 8-node reduced integration shell element with 5 degrees of freedom at each node has been used to discretise numerical models.

$E_{11}(GPa)$	$E_{22}(GPa)$	$G_{12} = G_{13}(GPa)$	$G_{23}(GPa)$	ν_{12}
138	11.0	5.50	3.93	0.278

Table 1: Material properties.

In order to compare the results with the analytical ones, it was essential that the FE analysis was conducted with boundary conditions identical to those as assumed in the analytical solution. For the analytical solution, the pre-buckling stress distribution was uniform. To achieve the same in FE analysis, the boundary conditions were specially prescribed to give perfectly uniform stress distributed as in the analytical solution. The four edges of structure was left free without any constraints of linear displacements except those to constrain rigid body motions at two reference points (RP) on the curved boundaries as depicted in Fig.2 (a), whilst the rotations at all nodes along the boundary were fixed to produce a pure membrane stress state. For the buckling analysis, tangential in-plane displacement and the rotation about the axis normal to the boundary are constrained along all boundary to reproduce simple support conditions as indicated in Fig.2 (b) to be consistent with the expressions of the buckling mode assumed in the analytical solution [1,16]. The same boundary conditions in buckling analysis have been used in the post-buckling regime. In addition, post-buckling stresses σ^2 which emerge through the analytical solution have been discretised and prescribed on the boundaries as shown in Fig.2 (c). Post-buckling σ^2 can be directly determined by Airy stress ϕ^2 . It should be noted here that the differentiation of the boundary conditions for pre-buckling and buckling analyses was artificial simply to be consistent with the analytical solution. Otherwise, the comparison between them would not be meaningful.

Figure 2: boundary conditions of simply supported shells in the pre-buckling (a), buckling (b) and post-buckling regimes (c).

3.2 Numerical results

In this paper, the number of half waves along the longitudinal direction of shallow shells is assigned to be 2 on purpose which indicates that the first initial post-buckling coefficient a vanishes in these circumstances. For the non-vanishing value of a , one can refer to another conference paper of authors [17]. Two sets of dimensions of shallow shells have been considered along with two stacking sequences for each one as presented in Table 2.

Layup	R(mm)	B(mm)	L(mm)	Buckling load (N/mm)		a		b	
				AS	NS	AS	NS (10^{-11})	AS	NS
[90/0/90/0]s	200	34.8	50	134.8	131.7	0	0.1207	0.1089	0.1536
[90/90/0/0]s	200	34.8	50	111.6	108.9	0	0.0860	0.0695	0.0171
[90/0/90/0]s	500	34.8	50	122.7	119.8	0	0.2762	0.6585	0.9821
[90/90/0/0]s	500	34.8	50	99.45	97.02	0	0.0213	0.8064	1.189

AS: analytical solution; NS: numerical solution

Table 2: Numerical results of plates

Figure 3: Secondary perturbation modes of shell with R=500, layup [90/0/90/0]s (a) AS, (b) NS

It can be easily found in Table 2 that the buckling loads have been precisely reproduced by numerical investigations when compared with analytical values. The vanishing values of a have been satisfactorily obtained as well with infinitesimal numerical results. However, the reproductions of b become not as acceptable as the buckling loads and a . With the consideration of initial post-buckling stresses for determinations of secondary perturbation modes, the boundary conditions are so complex that they cannot be readily and straightforwardly coped with. The reason of considerable differences between analytical and numerical values may be attributed to absence of in-plane displacements in the analytical analysis. Deflection as the main contribution to the final analytical results is the only factor considered. While, five degrees of freedom at every node have been simulated in the numerical examples which means that the deformation of structures have been fully taken into account without any ignorance.

4 REPRODUCTIONS OF SIMPLY-SUPPORTED PLATES UNDER COMPRESSION

As simplified cases of shallow shells, simply supported flat plates subject to uniaxial compression have been taken into account in this section. Likewise, both initial post-buckling coefficients have been calculated for comparisons.

4.1 Numerical models

Two plates with aspect ratio 1 and 2 have been modelled. The width of each plate is the same, 100mm. Similarly, cross-ply laminate with same layup $[90/0/90/0]_s$ has been considered for both scenarios. Same thickness of each layer, material properties and shell element as those for shells have been applied. To demonstrate the advancement in dealing with the numerical convergence problem, different mesh densities have been especially accounted.

To generate the pure membrane stress state in the pre-buckling regime, the translational displacements in the normal direction and two rotational displacements of four edges have been constrained. Two points A and B as shown in Fig.4 (a) have been chosen to fix the rigid body movement and applied in buckling and post-buckling regimes as well. In buckling analysis, the rotational displacements about each boundary have been set free. Accordingly, the secondary perturbation stresses from analytical solution have been prescribed on the boundaries as depicted in Fig.4 (c).

Figure 4: boundary conditions of plate in pre-buckling (a), buckling (b) and post-buckling regimes for aspect ratio=1 (c-1) and 2 (c-2)

4.2 Numerical results

The numbers of half waves of buckling modes along compression direction are one and two for two plates, respectively. Although plates are of with different lengths, the buckling loads and two initial post-buckling coefficients happen to be the same as shown in Table 3.

Layup	Aspect ratio	Mesh	Buckling load (N/mm)		a		b		
			AS	NS	AS	NS (10^{-13})	AS	NS	
$[90/0/90/0]_s$	L/B=1	10×10		14.58		0.1098		0.6333	
		15×15		14.58		0.0101		0.6400	
		20×20		14.58		0.2988		0.6333	
	L/B=2	25×25	14.65		14.58	0	0.6908	0.6304	0.6358
		15×7		14.58		0.0047		0.6396	
		25×11		14.59		0.0133		0.6351	
	33×17		14.59		0.0162		0.6341		
	45×23		14.59		0.1084		0.6335		

Table 3: Numerical results of plates

It can be noticed through Table 3 that the buckling loads and two initial post-buckling coefficients from numerical methods show excellent agreement with the analytical one. Either coarse or refined mesh density produces converged numerical results. Hence, the computational convergence problem which impeded the implementation of initial post-buckling theory into finite element context for decades has been completely resolved herein by using the newly-established N-notation for finite element formulation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

1. Koiter's initial post-buckling theory has been successfully implemented into finite element environment with commutative N-notation. The validation of this approach has been demonstrated through comparisons between numerical results and analytical ones.

2. Analytical derivations of initial post-buckling coefficients of simply supported shell have been proposed by using perturbation method. As a simplified version, the results of simply supported plate have been provided as well. Number of half waves along the longitudinal direction determines the vanishing or non-vanishing value of a . Sign of b of shell remains undecided. For plate, a is always equal to zero. The b is positive which implies a stable initial post-buckling behaviour of plate.

3. Two kinds of structural configurations have been modelled. Numerical results show great agreement with analytical ones due to precise boundary conditions from analytical solutions. The considerable differences of b for shell is presumably because of lack of in-plane displacement in analytical research.

4. Convergence problem which was encountered for decades has been entirely resolved in the fact of that different mesh densities produce the converged numerical results.

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